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HIPPARCOS / TYCHO

Computing effort for TYCHO data analysis

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1. Preliminaries

To estimate the computing effort for TYCHO it is necessary to describe the data analysis in some detail. This does not mean that the actual reductions will follow the precepts below - better methods will hopefully emerge when the critical problems are better understood and the hardware configuration more clearly defined.

The aim of TYCHO, as adopted for this study, is to detect and measure (photometrically and astrometrically) most stars down to $B \approx 11$, or about 400,000 stars, without a priori data on their positions.

The input data will consist of the complete photometric records of two star mappers (SM), each sampled at 600 Hz (this number may be lowered), and of the a posteriori attitude information derived from the HIPPARCOS reductions. The latter is assumed to be in the form of one vector $\underline{a} = (\alpha_z \ \delta_z \ \omega)^T$ per frame (2 sec interval); it is assumed that linear interpolation gives accurate enough inter-frame attitude (rms error $\sim 0''.1$).

Each SM will have two groups of slits, differently inclined with respect to the scanning direction. The configuration in Fig. 1 is used for the numerical examples, but other solutions would be possible too. The slit groups are identified by s, b = slash, backslash. A star passes in sequence Ab-As-Bs-Bb. The central line of each group is defined by a function $\eta_{As}(\zeta)$ etc. For the coincidence detection described below it is essential that corresponding groups are parallel to a high accuracy ($\sim 0''.1$), viz. in the sense

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_{As}(\zeta) - \eta_{Bs}(\zeta) &= D_s \quad (\text{independent of } \zeta), \\ \eta_{Ab}(\zeta) - \eta_{Bb}(\zeta) &= D_b \quad (\text{independent of } \zeta) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

A nominal scanning rate of $150''/\text{sec}$ is assumed. The precise arrangement of slits within each group (number, width and position) is not important, but for simplicity we assume that the same arrangement is used for b and s. The timing accuracy of star transits may be 1-3 ms, corresponding to $0''.15 - 0''.45$.

2. Preprocessing

For the simplest possible detection of transits the photometric sequence is fed to a linear numerical filter the output of which is proportional to the stellar brightness (at the correct time of transit). A detection (suspected transit) is recorded when the filter output exceeds a certain level, which may be chosen (depending on the background level) to give an acceptable rate of spurious detections. The length of the filter will be at least 120 points (= 30"); perhaps 200 points is more realistic if a more complex slit pattern is used to reduce problems with slit ambiguity.

Direct implementation of such a filter operating on each of the two photometric sequences requires about (2 sequences) $\times$ (200 filter points) $\times$ (600 samples/sec) = 240,000 multiplications/sec. Using FFT or some other clever algorithm a saving by a factor 5 may be realistic. On the other hand, two passes may be required to detect faulty data points and remove ghost detections caused by slit ambiguity; thus in total

$$\text{SM preprocessing} \sim 100,000 \text{ mult/sec.} \quad (2)$$

This includes the calculation of threshold, threshold comparison, interpolation of transit time, etc, which is a marginal effort by comparison.

The output of the preprocessing would consist of the following data per detection:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} - \text{transit time } (\tau) \\ - \text{amplitude of filter output } (a). \end{array} \right\} \sim 10 \text{ bytes/detection}$$

The average number of true transits per second is (2 SM) $\times$ (2 FOV) $\times$ (2 groups) $\times$ (10 stars/deg²) $\times$ (150"/sec) $\times$ (36') = 2 transits/sec. Let us assume that twice as many spurious detections occur; then about 250,000 transits are recorded per set (12 h interval), or $\approx$ 2.5 Mb.

3. Some recurrent tasks

We shall describe three typical tasks which form an essential part of the data analysis in that they have to be executed very frequently. Therefore it is particularly important to have realistic estimates of the computations involved in them.

3.1. Spherical transformation

This means the conversion of one set of angles (representing a point on the sphere or the orientation of a vector triad) into a similar set, using a transformation defined by three rotation angles. Examples:

$$\begin{aligned} (\alpha \delta) &\xleftrightarrow{\alpha_z \delta_z \omega} (\eta \zeta f) \\ (\alpha \delta) &\xleftrightarrow{\alpha_r \delta_r} (v \rho) \\ (\alpha_z \delta_z \omega) &\xleftrightarrow{\alpha_r \delta_r} (v_z \rho_z \omega') \\ (v \rho) &\xleftrightarrow{v_z \rho_z \omega'} (\eta \zeta f) \end{aligned}$$

[α_r, δ_r = pole of RGC (for a set); v, ρ = abscissa, ordinate (spherical coordinates referred to RGC. ($v_z \rho_z \omega'$) = attitude with respect to RGC.]

It appears that one such transformation takes about 12 trigonometric evaluations and some 40 multiplications; counting 8 mult/trig we have

$$\text{one spherical transformation} \sim 150 \text{ mult.} \quad (3)$$

A substantial saving is possible if several points are transformed by the same rotation angles; however, this applies rather seldom, so we adopt the rather conservative estimate (3).

3.2. Computation of a priori transit time

Given a star position $(v \rho)$ and the sequence of attitude angles $(v_z \rho_z \omega')$, calculate the time of transit (τ) at a particular slit group defined by its central line $\eta(\zeta)$.

Let t_k be the mid-time of a frame not far from the transit time. Compute the projections $(v_u \rho_u), (v_l \rho_l)$ on the sky of the upper and lower endpoints of the central line. The distance (along v) of the star from a 'straight line' between the two endpoints is then

$$\Delta v = [\rho(v_u - v_1) + \rho_1(v - v_u) + \rho_u(v_1 - v)]/(\rho_u - \rho_1). \quad (4)$$

Since $d(\Delta v)/dt \approx -dw/dt$ ($\approx -150''/\text{sec}$) we have as a first approximation

$$\tau = t_k + \Delta v(t_{k+1} - t_k)/(\omega_{k+1}^- - \omega_k^-). \quad (5)$$

This is improved by a single Newton-Raphson iteration: the attitude at time τ is interpolated and the field coordinates $(\eta \zeta)$ of $(v \rho)$ at time τ computed. Then the improved transit time is

$$\tau := \tau + [\eta - \eta(\zeta)](t_{j+1} - t_j)/(\omega_{j+1}^- - \omega_j^-), \quad (6)$$

where $t_j \leq \tau < t_{j+1}$.

The greater part of the computations are taken by the three spherical transformations; in total we have

$$\text{one computation of } \tau \sim 500 \text{ mult.} \quad (7)$$

3.3. Intersection of n central lines

Given $n \geq 2$ transits $\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n$ of the same star at different slit groups, defined by functions $\eta_i(\zeta)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, compute the most probable position $(v \rho)$.

A provisional position is first computed from the intersection of two 'straight lines' connecting the endpoints of two slit groups with different inclination, say transit no. i and j ($1 \leq i, j \leq n$). This requires 4 spherical transformations, yielding the upper/lower endpoints $(v_{ui} \rho_{ui})$, $(v_{li} \rho_{li})$, $(v_{uj} \rho_{uj})$, $(v_{lj} \rho_{lj})$. The point of intersection is

$$\rho = [(\rho_{ju} v_{j1} - \rho_{j1} v_{ju})/(\rho_{ju} - \rho_{j1}) - (\text{ditto for } i)]/(s_i - s_j), \quad (8)$$

$$v = v_{i1} + (\rho - \rho_{i1})s_i, \quad (9)$$

where $s = (v_u - v_1)/(\rho_u - \rho_1)$ are the slopes of the two lines in the $(v \rho)$ plane.

The position is then improved by one (least-squares) iteration: the field coordinates $(\eta_i \zeta_i)$ of $(v \rho)$ at transit times are calculated (n transformations) and observation equations formed,

$$\left[\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \nu} - \eta'(\zeta_1) \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \nu} \right] \Delta \nu + \left[\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \rho} - \eta'(\zeta_1) \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \rho} \right] \Delta \rho = \eta(\zeta_1) - \eta_1. \quad (10)$$

Calculation of the partial derivatives requires one more spherical transformation per transit. Least-squares solution of (10) yielding the corrections $\Delta \nu$, $\Delta \rho$ is a negligible effort. Thus

$$\text{intersection of } n \text{ transits} \sim (2n+4) \times 150 \text{ mult.} \quad (11)$$

4. Coincidence detection of transits

If the 250,000 detections recorded in a set were projected on the sky, there would result some 5 million intersections, each of which would have to be examined to give the likely locations of about 7000 stars. Since this is hardly practicable, we must drastically reduce the number of detections, and in particular the false detections, before combining them by intersections. One way would be to accept in a first pass only detections common to both SMs, i.e. separated by the correct time interval corresponding to the group separations D_s , D_b . The feasibility of this method is briefly examined here.

The average time interval between detections (one SM) corresponds to 50", while the timing accuracy ($\pm 3\sigma$) corresponds to a window of 1-3". Coincidence detection would then be powerful enough to eliminate most of the spurious detections, provided that the time difference is independent (to $\sim 1''$) of the unknown ζ coordinate. This requires the corresponding slit groups to be accurately parallel, eqn (1), but also imposes constraints on the transverse attitude motion (rotation components not aligned with $\underline{z}$), as explained below.

In terms of the rotation vector in the telescope frame, $\underline{\omega}' \equiv (\omega_x \ \omega_y \ \omega_z)'$, the time derivative of the field coordinates of an inertially fixed direction is

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\eta} &= \tan \zeta [\omega_x \cos(\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma) + \omega_y \sin(\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma)] - \omega_z, \\ \dot{\zeta} &= -\omega_x \sin(\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma) + \omega_y \cos(\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma). \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Integrating along the path from SMA to SMB we obtain to first order in $\omega_{x,y}/\omega_z$,

$$\begin{aligned} t_B - t_A &= \frac{D}{\omega_z} \left[1 + (\tan \zeta \cos \frac{1}{2}\gamma \pm \eta'(\zeta) \sin \frac{1}{2}\gamma) (\omega_x/\omega_z) + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + (\pm \tan \zeta \sin \frac{1}{2}\gamma - \eta'(\zeta) \cos \frac{1}{2}\gamma) (\omega_y/\omega_z) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where ζ and $\omega_x, \omega_y, \omega_z$ are now to be interpreted as suitable averages along the path. Knowing the attitude motion ($T'\omega$), but not ζ , it is seen that the uncertainty is of the order of $(t_B - t_A) \tan \zeta_{\max} |\omega_{x,y}/\omega_z| < 1''$ if $|\omega_{x,y}/\omega_z| < 0.02$, which seems fairly reasonable.

Moreover it is seen that the time interval will be different between the two fields (p and f, denoted by upper and lower sign in the equations) by a known amount, $(D/\omega_z) \times 2\eta^-(\zeta) \sin \frac{1}{2}\gamma(\omega_x/\omega_z) > 3''$ if $\omega_x/\omega_z > 0.001$ [with $\eta^-(\zeta) \approx \pm 0.5$].

Thus, if the transverse rotations are less than $0.02\omega_z \approx 3''/\text{sec}$ (corresponding to a misalignment between $\underline{z}$ and $\underline{\omega}$ of about 1°), but typically greater than $0.001\omega_z \approx 0.15''/\text{sec}$ ($3'$), the coincidence method should be useful, not only to reject spurious detections, but also to decide the slit group (b/s) and field (p/f) of accepted detections.

A/B coincidence detection would then require the following steps:

- (i) Take one SMA detection (τ_A).
- (ii) Hypothesis bp: τ_A is a transit at group b of the p-field. Putting $\zeta = 0$ (since $t_B - t_A$ is anyhow independent of ζ) we obtain ($\nu \rho$) by a spherical transformation; then the computed transit τ_B at SMB, according to Section 3.2. Check if there is in fact an SMB detection in the interval $\tau_B \pm 3\sigma$; if so, compute a likelihood measure of the coincidence (L_{bp}), based also e.g. on the amplitude match.
- (iii) - (v) Make similar calculations for hypotheses bf, sp, and sf.
- (vi) If $\max(L_{bp}, L_{bf}, L_{sp}, L_{sf}) > L_0$, accept corresponding hypothesis.
- (vii) Take next SMA detection and repeat (i) - (vi).

In this way every detection is either rejected or accepted; in the latter case, it is assigned to a particular group (b/s) and field (p/f). The processing of one SMA detection takes $4 \times (150 + 500 + \dots) + \dots = 3000$ multiplications; with 3 SMA detections per second we get

$$\text{A/B coincidence detection} \sim 9000 \text{ mult/sec.} \quad (14)$$

To estimate the resulting frequency of true and false coincidences, let us assume:

- (a) that the probability of detecting a true transit at a single group is 0.8;
- (b) that each SM produces one true and two false detections per second;

(c) that a pair of A/B detections is accepted as a coincidence if the time interval is correct to within $\pm 10 \text{ ms} = \pm 1.5''$.

Then if the SMA detection is false (which happens twice per second), the probability of getting a coincidence is (4 hypotheses) $\times$ (20 ms window) $\times$ (3 SMB detections/sec) = 0.24. Thus, 0.48 false/false or false/true coincidences are produced per second. If the SMA detection is true (once per second), the probability of a true/true coincidence is taken to be 0.8, while that of a true/false coincidence is $(1 - 0.8) \times 0.24 = 0.05$. The net result is therefore, in round figures, 0.8 true and 0.6 false coincidences per second. Each coincidence is about 20 bytes.

If a star is to be located, it must be detected both as an Ab/Bb and an As/Bs coincidence, the probability of which is only $0.8^4 = 0.4$. However, a given star will pass the Ab-As-Bs-Bb configuration some 70 times during the mission, so it is not likely that it escapes detection altogether.

In view of this it seems reasonable to require also coincidence between the two fields (p/f), in order to reduce even more the number of false detections. Due to the transverse attitude motion the two fields, when passing the same star, will be slightly misaligned, perhaps by about $10'$. Due to the unknown ζ coordinate, the p/f coincidence window must then be of the order of $10''$, giving a probability of chance coincidence $(10'' \text{ window}) \times (\frac{1}{150} \text{ sec}/'') \times (0.7 \text{ f-coincidences/sec}) = 0.05$. With similar arguments as above we obtain the rates: 0.2 true and 0.03 false p/f coincidences per second. Each coincidence will be about 40 bytes, and

$$\text{p/f coincidence detection} \sim 400 \text{ mult/sec.} \quad (15)$$

5. Calculation of candidate locations

Each intersection of the various Abp-Bbp-Abf-Bbf and Asp-Bsp-Asf-Bsf coincidences (about 0.11 per second of each kind) represents a candidate location for a $B \leq 11$ star. They are obtained by combining each b-coincidence with every s-coincidence within a time interval compatible with the width of the b/s configuration, viz. $\approx 36' / (150''/\text{sec}) = 15 \text{ sec}$. Candidate locations are thus produced at a rate of $(15 \text{ sec}) \times (0.11 \text{ b-coinc/sec}) \times (0.11 \text{ s-coinc/sec}) = 0.18 \text{ loc/sec}$, or $\sim 10^7$ for the entire mission. Since one intersection ($n = 8$) takes about 5000 multiplications, including a transformation to $(\alpha \delta)$,

$$\text{calculation of candidate locations} \sim 900 \text{ mult/sec.} \quad (16)$$

One candidate location would probably need about 20 bytes. Only about 1/5 of the 10 million locations will correspond to real stars; these are clustered within a few arcsec from the 400,000 true locations, while the remaining candidate locations are spread out fairly uniformly over the sphere (one would hope), yielding an average separation of about 250". One would need a sort of random access to this catalogue, with the candidate locations ordered in a systematic way (e.g. in declination zones after increasing right ascension), so that the coincidences of two or more locations can be found without too much searching. This should then be a comparatively small effort compared to (16), although the data management problems would not be easy. The process should result in a sub-catalogue of perhaps 10^6 preliminary locations to be further examined.

6. Second pass

The preliminary locations must then be directly compared with the original sequence of detections. If we look at one 12 h set, covering about 700 deg^2 , there are about 17,000 preliminary locations which should first be transformed to $(\alpha \delta)$: $2.5 \cdot 10^6$ mult. During the 12 hours they will produce 200,000 transits: $1.0 \cdot 10^8$ mult. These are compared with the 250,000 observed detections, from which most of the 80,000 true detections are obtained, yielding observation equations like (10) to be saved: $7 \cdot 10^7$ mult. Thus a total of $2 \cdot 10^8$ mult are needed for each set of the second pass.

7. Adding up

For the whole mission (about 1800 sets or $7 \cdot 10^7$ sec) the computing effort for each stage of the SM data processing will be as follows.

processing stage	no. of mult.	amount of data, type of access
preprocessing	$7 \cdot 10^{12}$	100,000 Mb sequential (raw data)
A/B coincidence	$7 \cdot 10^{11}$	5,000 Mb - " -
p/f coincidence	$3 \cdot 10^{10}$	2,000 Mb - " -
calculation of candidate locations	$7 \cdot 10^{10}$	700 Mb - " -
second pass	$4 \cdot 10^{11}$	200 Mb random
		20 Mb - " - (TYCHO Catalogue)
	sum total $8 \cdot 10^{12}$	

The first thing to notice is perhaps that the preprocessing seems to require by far the greatest effort. A few comments are appropriate:

(a) The amount of preprocessing goes as the square of the SM sampling rate. Since it may be sufficient to sample at 300 Hz, a reduction by a factor 4 may be feasible. Moreover, most of the arithmetic can be made in integer or fixed-point format (whereas the other processing stages usually require floating-point or sometimes even double-precision arithmetic). This would probably reduce the preprocessing to about the same size as the remaining reductions.

(b) The basic algorithm involved in the preprocessing, i.e. a finite-length linear filter, is so simple that it may be advantageous to do most of the preprocessing with specially designed hardware or microprocessors.

(c) To avoid handling thousands of magnetic tapes it is very desirable that the preprocessing is made at ESOC, even if it were considered the responsibility of the data reduction consortia.

(d) As for the remaining stages, they could realistically be carried out on a minicomputer system including a big disc (≥ 100 Mb) and two 1600 or 6250 bpi tape units. It should be noted that all stages up to the second pass can be executed as data come along, using only the preliminary attitude information available at that time from the HIPPARCOS reductions.

(e) Finally, if a priori positions of the TYCHO stars were available, from photographic surveys or meridian observations, only the preprocessing and second pass of the reductions would be needed, cutting the post-preprocessing by a factor 3 or 4.

FIGURE 1.